

Valentino Syndrome: A Surgical Emergency with Appendicitis-Like Presentation

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ABSTRACT: Valentino Syndrome is a rare but potentially serious medical condition.

In this article, we discuss the case of a 39-year-old chronic smoker who presented with right iliac fossa pain evolving for 15 days. The symptoms worsened four days before admission with the onset of generalized abdominal pain accentuated in the epigastric region, with a history of recent NSAID intake for right iliac fossa pain. A chest X-ray revealed pneumoperitoneum, with a CT scan confirming hydropneumoperitoneum. The patient was urgently taken to the operating room, where exploration revealed a large amount of purulent peritoneal effusion, a 1 cm perforation in the pylorus with soft edges, subhepatic and interloop adhesions at the Douglas pouch, cecum, and terminal ileum, a gastrocolic fistula between the cecum and 40 cm of the colon, sealed by the greater omentum, and a perforated and digested appendix. The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on postoperative day 5 after drain removal and incident-free feeding.

KEYWORDS: ulcer perforation, appendicitis, Valentino syndrome.

INTRODUCTION

Gastroduodenal ulcer is a defect in the mucosa of the stomach or duodenum. Perforation of the stomach or duodenum is one of the serious complications of gastroduodenal ulcer that requires emergency medical care.

Valentino Syndrome is a rare entity, first described in 1926 in actor Rudolph Valentino, who initially presented with symptoms of acute appendicitis and was operated on for this condition. Following surgery, he developed peritonitis, multi-organ dysfunction, and died after several days. Autopsy revealed a perforated gastric ulcer, with gastric contents reaching the right paracolic gutter, causing peritoneal irritation mimicking acute appendicitis(1).

It poses a diagnostic challenge for radiologists and surgeons. The aim of this article is to highlight the importance of meticulous surgical exploration, especially in smokers or patients known to have gastritis due to Helicobacter pylori infection or recent NSAID use.

OBSERVATION

We present the case of a 39-year-old chronic smoker with a 10 pack-year history, presenting with right iliac fossa pain evolving for 15 days, worsened by generalized abdominal pain four days before admission, accentuated in the epigastric region, with no other associated signs. On clinical examination, there was generalized abdominal rigidity. The patient reported recent NSAID use for right iliac fossa pain.

A chest X-ray revealed pneumoperitoneum.

Figure 1: plain abdominal radiography showing pneumoperiton.

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Abdominal CT scan showed hydro pneumoperitoneum suggestive of probable ulcer perforation.

Figure 2: CT scan showing a hydro-pneumoperitoneum.

Figure 3: pelvic stage on CT scan.

The patient was urgently taken to the operating room, where exploration revealed a large amount of purulent peritoneal effusion, a 1 cm pyloric perforation with soft edges, subhepatic and interloop adhesions at the Douglas pouch, cecum, and terminal ileum, a gastrocolic fistula between the cecum and 40 cm of the colon sealed by the greater omentum, and a perforated and digested appendix. The procedure involved suturing a 1 cm pyloric perforation with pyloroplasty and epiplooplasty, ileocecal resection, and double-barreled ileocolostomy, with peritoneal lavage and drainage.

The postoperative course was uneventful, with functional stoma on postoperative day 1 and minimal serous drain output. The patient was discharged on postoperative day 5 after drain removal and incident-free feeding.

Figure 4: image showing adhesions in interloop.

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Figure 5: image showing the gastric perforation.

Figure 6: image of the caecal fistula; 1: caecal perforation; 2: ileal perforation.

Figure 7: image of the digested appendicular base.

DISCUSSION

Valentino Syndrome was first described in 1926(2).

Despite its rarity, it is crucial to better understand this syndrome to improve diagnosis and management of affected patients.

Peptic gastric or duodenal ulcers result from *H. pylori* infection, use of NSAIDs and steroids, smoking, alcoholism, and Zollinger-Ellison syndrome(3).

Perforation is one of the complications of peptic ulcers, with increased mortality(4).

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Uncomplicated peptic ulcer presents with epigastric pain, bloating, nausea, and sometimes melena and hematemesis(5).

Perforation of these ulcers is considered a surgical emergency with increased morbidity and mortality if perforation duration exceeds 24 hours and size exceeds 1 cm(6).

Valentino Syndrome should be suspected when signs and symptoms of acute appendicitis accompany epigastric pain and/or recent NSAID consumption, as seen in our patient(1).

This symptomatology is explained by the passage of gastric contents through a perforated peptic ulcer into the right iliac fossa, causing inflammation and leading to symptoms and signs similar to acute appendicitis(3).

Imaging typically reveals air in the right retroperitoneum and around the right kidney(1).

Treatment primarily involves suturing the gastric perforation either laparoscopically or by laparotomy, with or without appendectomy depending on intraoperative appendix appearance.

Management also includes treatment for H. pylori eradication.

CONCLUSION

Valentino Syndrome is a rare entity representing a significant diagnostic challenge due to its clinical presentation similar to acute appendicitis, highlighting the importance of thorough surgical exploration to identify the cause of peritonitis, emphasizing the role of laparoscopic surgery.

Early diagnosis and management are essential to prevent serious complications associated with this condition.

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